

The Role and Importance of Communicating Science for Building up Understanding of Science Applications

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Article Info	Abstract
Article History	<p><i>Enhancing understating of science is a need to build up school community and society. The techniques and tactics utilized by a community of science teachers to incorporate and teach skills. The study explores science teachers' views of communicating science to the school community and society. The data were collected through semi-structured interviews from 15 science teachers with more than 5 years of teaching experience and teaching Physics, Chemistry and Biology at the secondary level. Interview data-informed science teachers' understanding of communication science to the school community and society involves disseminating profound knowledge of the scientific facts and applications used in their lives. The results pointed out that the secondary level teachers had faced various difficulties in enhancing their understanding of science; therefore, schools need to develop a communication strategy to develop correct science concepts. They also agreed that science communication played an important role in the life of the student. Furthermore, science is more effective and valuable for students in their practical life. At the school level, lack of facilities and technology, lack of communicating mediums and laboratories, lack of experience of science teachers, lack of students' interest, only oral communication practices, and lack of practical activities are the significant difficulties in communicating science. We can overcome these difficulties by developing students' interest in science communication and making a proper environment for science communication.</i></p>
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Introduction

Communicating research findings to the general public is increasingly important to build support for science, making it diverse and, depending on the research, fostering informed decision-making within a community and governmental level. Good examples include controversial issues such as climate change, hydraulic fracturing, nuclear energy, stem cells, genetically modified organisms and other outputs that can solve societal problems. This chapter is a general introduction of the research work being carried out on Science communication. It is a practice of informing, educating, sensitizing, and enhancing the discovery rate of new things and their influences on them worldwide. Science communication is the practice of exposing the various things that help in the future for further development in positive and effective ways. The communicators of science and their listeners are defined ambiguously, and science skills and all levels vary from each group. The science outreach (naturally led by specialists to word the non-experience viewers) and science's reach are two types of defined scientific communication (from skilled to skilled from similar or different scientific backgrounds). The communicators of science could be used to entertaining and persuading, including various types of humor, account, and metaphors. Scientists could be trained in a few of the methods used by actors in improving their communicating skills (Grushkin, 2010). Continuous evaluation of science and engagement allows for a resource-efficient engagement design but avoids well-known dangers (Jensen & Gerber, 2020).

Science communication can generate and support scientific research and inform decision-making connected with ethical thinking and applications (Gregory & Miller, 1998). (Jensen & Gerber, 2020) also suggested that tackling scientific misinformation can be an effective medium between different groups and individuals to connect with public policy, industry, and civil society. According to (Kochhar, 1992), people lack scientific explanation and confidence about science applications and young people's lack of interest in understanding science disciplines' various studies and careers. It has also been confirmed by some variations in the theme, national and international youth and science surveys. A report published by (Oecd, 2007) about children shows natural curiosity and science and technology; many researchers also say that children act as "little scientists" in their approach to the world around them. However, the student's interest disappears completely from these subjects in a traditional path of science education and communication, affecting schools and communities in education and career choices; therefore, this study attempts to fulfill the gap to explore further the role of communicating science to school community and society.

Review of the related Literature

The literature is relevant to the role and importance of science communication to the school community; accentuate some recent studies with the appropriate theme. In recent years, (L'Astorina & Valente, 2011) described the lack of attractiveness of scientific careers among new science students. This is argued that the insufficient diffusion of scientific culture and dissemination of knowledge about various useful appliances of science have been surveyed on science and technology in many countries. Many factors present through which this technique affects properly and inappropriate manner. If science communication does not practice, then students lack an understanding of scientific inquiry and process. Saying this, the parents and society also benefit from the students' understanding and literacy if the science students are well communicated about the application of science. Communication science might improve the awareness of science as a practical means of experiencing the natural environment and handling it. Though not thoroughly evaluated, this objective suggests that people who have more understanding of science, who are more familiar with science, who have a general store of science-related facts, and who respect science and its function in acquiring knowledge would be more likely to include scientific information (science-based expertise and how it is generated) in their decision-making processes. Communicators should also aim to enhance the general awareness of knowledge among individuals, improve the quality of life, assist in decision-making, and extend the basis of scientific evidence widely utilized by the public, including elected authorities, corporate representatives, or private people. More educated choices will benefit from combining this information with principles and other related factors.

Science communication has several advantages in promoting awareness and the best interest of society and the school community. Libutti and Valente (2006) explained the perceptions of the relationship between science and culture. Burns et al. (2003a) stated that collaboration in science is an increasing field of experience and study. The number of events, classes, and practitioners has gradually risen over the past two decades. But really, what is collaboration in science? How is general knowledge of science, public comprehension of science, scientific history, and scientific literacy separate from that? To put together a detailed collection of meanings for these similar concepts, the writers study the literature. A unifying mechanism is presented and within this context, a contemporary idea of scientific communication is imposed. Science communication (SciCom) is characterized as appropriate skills, media, activities, and discussion to elicit knowledge, enjoyment, curiosity, opinion-forming, and comprehension. The concept offers an outcome-type understanding of communication in science, which provides the framework for more study and assessment.

Dialogue has been vital in science communications in Van der Sanden and Meijman (2008). Many efforts by the government, like knowledge transfer, utilize dialog as a point of sale. For e.g., we have a GM dialog, a science future dialog in Europe, and the Food Protection Dialogue. In reality, the dialog has become a medium of contact, apart from public knowledge and research. Dialog is, however, just a technique, a process that can accomplish all of its purposes in every condition of scientific communication. (Trench, 2008) investigated science communication at public relations models of scientific communications circles on the debate of science and technology. Scientists constantly communicate in talks, papers, classrooms, proposals, and elsewhere. The 30-second elevator pitch is suddenly taking far too long. Video clips start playing automatically. The quality of scientific discovery is just as excellent as its dissemination; The idea is to account for the various communication channels that result from the finding. When scientists organize data differently, they can find more connections themselves. Colleagues will be able to reproduce experiments more readily. (Murcia, 2009). When writing up the research, professional writers would have more significant context. Even during the interpersonal process, reviewers can observe more of the scientists' thought processes and routes.

Internationally, the education system is increasingly recognized as having its share of responsibility. The school frequently stresses this distance when it offers workshops, courses and textbooks which present a diluted science without its dynamics, which contradicts and is often taken out of its original context, application and multi-disciplinary comparison (Caravita et al., 2008). In the same way, the report on research and education by the European project 'Form it,' pointed out that there were two reasons for lack of interest in the sciences which directly relate to school: the contents of science, abstract, and far away from the everyday lives of students; and teaching methods, which are based on lessons using a deductive method that is seldom particulate (Murcia, 2009).

A few years back, a board of European specialists or scientists in new instructional ideas for science instructing categorized the Research and Education Cooperation (REC), that is the mutual alliance between an exploration assistant (e.g., public or private science or innovation research organization) and an educational one (e.g., schools, singular instructors, understudies or understudies), as a highly encouraging and exhaustive methodology, ready to essentially add to redesign science training and correspondence and to beat the hole between youngsters and science (Gerloff-Gasser et al., 2007).

(Gregory & Miller, 1998) suggested that community understanding of science was low on the plan. Nevertheless, some notable figures, e.g., Michael Faraday, ran speeches focused on the non-master community, his being the well-known Christmas Speeches in 1825. The twentieth century saw bunches established on the

ground. They could situate science in a more wide-ranging social setting and authority researchers to convey their insight in a method that could reach and be supposed by the world's overall population. In the abroad countries such as in the UK, The Bodmer Report distributed in 1985 by The Royal Society changed how researchers communicated their work to people in a general way so common peoples are easily approached to their research. The report was intended to "review the nature and degree of the public understanding of science in the United Kingdom and its amplexness for high-level equality.

The main and vital use of Information and Communications Technology (ICT) has made tremendous progress in education in established and emerging countries and brought educational reform by changing teacher and learner roles. This is most use effectively in various developed countries of the world also including Pakistan. This is also limited in developing countries, such as Pakistan, due to costs and scarce resources. Its extent and coverage in human civilization are unprecedented because of access to information, communication, knowledge, and entertainment. The new techniques tools have altered how people can communicate and transform the various life routine activities, including industry, agriculture, medicine, enterprise, engineering, and other sectors. It can change the nature of education setup, the methodology of teaching the audience, and the vital role of students and teachers in learning and communicating. However, this technique has a positive role in life; the other diverse impact of new technologies redefines how teachers and learners access knowledge. To meet these trials, schools must be used such tools to teach and learn to transform the traditional teaching examples (Williams & Sawyer, 2007).

Also, teachers and schools play a significant role in communicating appliances to society and parents by using ICT. Science teachers were getting trendy in improving their basic ICT knowledge and skills. Computers can be installed in individual classrooms, central computer laboratories, libraries and teacher planning rooms or moved from room to mobile carts to enhance the use of computers in schools and achieve the educational targets that need it (Pandey, 2004).

Moreover, technology includes tools and machines; it impacts processes and systems, society, and people's thinking, perception, and definition of their world. In the last few decades, almost all aspects of human life have reached a particular technological dimension. The most important is IT, commonly called Information technology that includes computers, computer software, the Internet and electronic multimedia, is increasingly becoming part of our daily life. This reality also means that information technology must be integrated into curricula for various subjects (Mishra, 2005).

Additionally, the teachers play the most critical role in implementing one of these types of communication in a community. ICT is also an essential communicational skill, which many teachers in the school use. The most significant drawbacks of such conditions are the lack of information about ICT knowledge and expertise. For example, it was a significant impediment to its implementation and, therefore, highlighted the need for the training of teachers in this field. If education provides adequate future preparation, schools need to enable students to become more active and accountable for their learning processes (Pelgrum & Law, 2003).

In the broadest sense, absorbing science communication is sharing science-related information whereby one activity perceptibly affects information customers (Burns et al., 2003b). Like teaching, there is no single way to deal with science communication (Weigold, 2001), and in this way, no single formula for progress. Researchers' reasons for participating in science correspondence likewise fluctuate (Poliakoff & Webb, 2007), including award necessities, a genuine interest in genuine commitment, and sensations of exemplary commitment. The proposed results of science correspondence exercises likewise range from changing human conduct to teaching, advising, or engaging a crowd of people. The most productive solution to the communication of research would focus on the communication purpose. Five wide and conflicting priorities for science communication are established by the commission, each of which puts very different demands on the expertise and skills of science communicators and their audiences and calls for a separate method of its own. These purposes provide a broad variety of motivations for contact, from educating listeners to inspiring people, organizations, or societies. The targets can be endpoints or aims that fulfill a greater purpose that justifies the transmission of science concepts by the communicator.

Also, raising consciousness and appreciation of science is relevant to a particular topic that needs a decision. In this situation, communicators may advise or teach individuals about science-related facts, how they were extracted from those facts, and what they represent for the decision. Communicators may focus on an overlooked topic or neglected facets of a problem or may want to increase the nature of an issue's debate by enhancing the media coverage of the related research. It is essential to note that an essential purpose of science communication may be to change the person's views, attitudes, and priorities. It is evident from the weight of facts that such actions have implications for public health, public protection, or other social problems. For example, communicators have sought to make people conscious of the positives of exercising, the risks of smoking and the value of blood pressure regulation. In those situations, communicators can be obligated to advise and convince individuals to modify their actions or make a policy decision. Communicators may also attempt to manipulate public opinion, e.g., healthcare or infrastructure gains or threats, to promote a particular plan.

The fifth purpose of science communication is to include different communities to search for solutions to social issues that impact all of them with a view to science (especially disputes). The systematic public participation method, sometimes used for social justice, which is technically, morally, and politically challenging, are distinguished by a high degree of scientific, technical and societal complexity, which is difficult to understand by the lack of appropriate expertise (including researchers outside of those areas of expertise); (Scheufele, 2014). Within and beyond the science world, Makers have called for more significant interaction with the general public by researchers to resolve all these complexities (Leshner, 2003).

Science cannot satisfy societal knowledge requirements or speak to all problems for these or other realistic or technical purposes such as the limits of available scientific methods. Scientific communication as a public involvement that applies to all communication between scientists and scientists and not just the official mechanism of people's engagement offers all stakeholders the ability to debate before it is established or implemented the possible threats, advantages and implications of technology. Communication of research findings is embedded in an academic's job description. Scientists give presentations, write papers for journals, communicate with funders through reports and the general public through mass media to inform and educate. There is no doubt that to be a successful scientist, you must be a good communicator. Increasingly, funding body's request, from the early stages of grant proposals, examples of how research can build on and expand the existing knowledge and its impact on society and governmental policy. Conferences, workshops, symposia and publications are considered to impact activities because they can generate debate while communicating findings to all stakeholders.

As science is increasingly interdisciplinary, effective communication is crucial to bring forward understanding, collaboration and innovation. Communicating the relevance and impact of your research findings will also secure further funding and help your academic career. At an intellectual level, sharing research can generate collaborations among experts and inspire new topics to investigate. Science museums have an essential function in science communication. Various models involving inventions exist in the museums, and students have visited to get inspiration and information. Diverse school communities also get inspiration from science and technology. It plays the role of practical communication. There are static displays of objects related to history, geology, planetology, and industrial machinery in the Museums.

In our digital age, the channels of communications have increased. Researchers are likely to engage their audiences with reports, conferences, and peer-reviewed articles in journals, media interviews, tweets, blogs, and public webinars. Science communication informs, educates, shares achievement and raises awareness of research findings. It includes science outreach scientists to non-expert audiences, usually through public events, mass and digital media and science in reach scientists to experts, conducted through scholarly communication, typically publication in scientific journals and conferences, which often generate published proceedings. As given above, the study explores how various ways of communicating science builds up an understanding of science applications.

Objectives of the Study

There are the following objectives

- To explore teachers' views of the role of communication of science to the school community and society.
- To find out the benefits of science communication to the school community in building up an understanding of science applications
- To explore the difficulties in communicating science in the schools

Research Questions of the study

There are the following research questions

- How do the science teachers view the role of communication of science to the school community?
- What are the benefits of science communication to the school community in building up an understanding of science applications?
- What are the difficulties in the communication of science in the school community?

Research Methodology

This research seeing a significant aspect of the role of computer-based applications, can elaborate upon such influences. It has been noticed that the frequency of published qualitative research studies is, however, comparatively lower than qualitative research in Pakistan. Accordingly, qualitative approaches like the interview, focus groups and observations provided in-depth views on the particular theme. The population of the study will consist of science teachers who are teaching science using qualitative approaches such as semi-structured interviews. The interviews were conducted in this study with 15 science teachers teaching.

Findings from the Interview Data

Interview data emerged the following themes and sub-themes:

- Understandings about Science Communication**
- Advantages of Science Communication in enhancing Science Understanding**
- Difficulties in Communicating Science**

Theme 1: Understandings about Science Communication

Interview data inform this research about participants' understanding of science communications. The majority of science teachers agree with the importance of science communication on the concepts of science applications. For example, T2 said, "Science communication contributes to the awareness of scientific objects in the classroom. Students are an important factor of the school community; they should be acquainted with the advanced knowledge of science." It is clear from his view that students are an important factor of the school community; they should be trained with advanced scientific knowledge. The teachers can only communicate science with the understanding of daily life use of scientific objects. Another opinion shows, for example, T4 said, "Teachers can only communicate science and findings of science when they get up to date knowledge of scientific literature. Science Literacy is one of the main objectives of the reform of science education. Students understand the importance of science and its communication. For example, T8 said that "science education only requires materials for learning." According to them, material here means practical work like apparatus.

Thus, Science communication is an interactive process involving mutual respect between researchers, educators and learners and a common language of communication. Almost all the interviewees answered this question, and Different interviewees were dealing in different branches of science. Interviewees were teaching biology, physics, chemistry, and mathematics and computer science. They had different teaching experiences. Few were teaching their related subject for a long time, and few were new in the field. Some were enjoying their teachings, but some of them were facing difficulties. Experience and way of communicating science were the reasons behind this.

The participants showed their views about how they experience teaching science and communication about science from the interviews. T1 said, "teaching their students by using a whiteboard, books, and animation from mobile. Some of them taught the students through practical work by using Urdu and English in elementary form. I always try to know the natural phenomenon". Therefore, Teaching their students by using a whiteboard, books, animation from mobile is not adequate. Some of them taught the students through practical work by using Urdu and English in elementary form. I always try to know the natural phenomena. Three interviewees said they communicate science using entertainment, stories, ancient science discoveries, and modern technology. They also use a sense of humor to interact with students. One interviewee said that he teaches his students by using a whiteboard, books, practical performance. For example, T4 said, "students by using a whiteboard, books, functional version.

Moreover, another teacher said that he communicates in experimental and practical language. Through valuable works and experiments, students learning are enhanced". For example, T9 said, "there is a computer availability which promotes students and enhances learning and understanding skills because through the computer-assisted communication of science includes audio-video descriptions along with images and short animations regarding science literacy and inventions in the world of science that helps students to understand and build conceptual learning. Thus, there is a computer availability that promotes students and enhances learning and understanding skills by story. Computer-assisted communication of science includes audio-video descriptions and images and short animations regarding science literacy and inventions in the world of science that help students understand and build conceptual learning.

Theme 2: Advantages of Science Communication in enhancing understanding of science applications

There are countless benefits of communicating science. Three interviewees believe that for students at the secondary level, it has been discussed that society can be promoted through scientific instruments, which are scientific inventions. There are countless benefits of communicating science. Students can get help in their future life. Advancement in medical and control of diseases can be possible by communication science and doing science.

T8 said, "For students at the secondary level. It has been discussed that society can be promoted through scientific instruments which are scientific inventions". Moreover, another example, T4, said, "Advancement in the field of medical and control of diseases can be possible by communication science and doing science." Through science, communication, educational achievements and social development can be done. Science creates awareness to students in which direction they can move in the future. It often results in published features. Things about education can influence student's as well as public opinion, behavior and policy priorities. Science affects people's lives, such as vaccination, medical care, education, food, etc. T14 said, "Increase knowledge of students. Practical work enhances the practice of students on hand to hand activities". Thus to dum up, through science, communication, educational achievements and social development can be done. Science creates awareness to students in which direction they can move in the future. It often results in published features. Concentrate on the difference between new approaches to public health and practitioners/politicians' awareness. Therefore, it is essential to link academia, industry, and government to change the quality and improve the quality of life.

Theme 3: Difficulties in Communicating Science

The data indicates various difficulties which affect communication negatively and are considered as problems in touch. But when we investigated challenges at the school level, we did not find these barriers in

communicating science. There were some other difficulties that teachers were facing in communicating science. For example, T3 said; *Various factors affected communication negatively and were considered as problems in communication.* And for example, T5 said, *“At the school level, teachers are not facing geographical issues; however, they face cultural and social issues because students belong to different communities and their backgrounds are also different.”* Teachers are not facing geographical issues; however, they face cultural and social issues because students belong to different communities within a school, and their backgrounds are also different. These aspects of their background impact students' attitudes towards understanding science communication in their classrooms and homes. At the school level, teachers are facing difficulties in communicating science. T15 said, *“Background of students do not support. Ground reality and our education system are opposite”*. From the interviews, it is clear that teachers face different difficulties communicating science at secondary level schools. Some teachers said that the Background of students does not support it. Moreover, the science teachers said teachers are not appropriately trained about science communication; sometimes, communication is ineffective and doesn't affect students. For example, T12 highlighted, *“There is an understanding problem with students. Superstitions are also there. Students have not basic knowledge”*.

Thus the teachers are not aware of scientific inventions and the previous history of science. T6 said, *“At the school level, lack of facilities and technology, lack of experience of teachers, lack of interest of students, only oral communication, and lack of practical activities are the difficulties in communicating science.* From the above data, it is clear that teachers were facing various troubles in science communication at the school level.

It is noted that every culture has its standards, styles and ethical principles that can exacerbate communication problems when students of various cultural backgrounds interact. Socio-cultural distances are national, organizational, political and moral backgrounds, which increase the chance of misunderstandings that may have a negative impact on the performance of teams. Students with different cultures usually learn on the same subject and curriculum, making learning together tricky. Social and cultural distance is directly influenced science communications in the classroom. As students belong to various backgrounds and families, status also varies, directly affecting students' understanding abilities. Students belong those families where illiterate parents are dominated; students cannot understand the lessons even if they cannot read labels. Language is one of the fundamental issues. Students do not know English, but the curriculum is English; thus, students and teachers feel the misunderstanding problem. For example, T6 believed, *“Through practical work and relating the things with daily life examples they can teach their students and effectively communicate science.* To overcome difficulties in communicating, science teachers have different strategies. The respondents believe they can teach their students and effectively communicate science through practical work and relating things with daily life examples.

Few emphasize computer-assisted learning in the age of COVID-19. Through computer and technology-assisted learning, teachers can communicate science in a very effective way. Computer-aided learning can be as effective as classroom teaching tools. For example, T1 said, *“We can easily communicate science through board presentation, computer-assisted science communication, practical work, etc.* Through practical work in labs, reducing socio-culture distance and computer-assisted learning difficulties can be overcome. The communicating and learning process uses a combination of graph, text, sound, and video. Computer-assisted instructions apply to nearly any application, such as exercises, simulations, teaching exercises, additional exercises, instructional management, database creation and programming.

Discussions

The data revealed how the participants interpreted the communication behavior. All of the participants had a great interest in teaching and communicate science. Teachers teaching science subjects had faced different difficulties. To teach and communicate science is not so easy. At the school level, lack of facilities and technology, lack of experience of teachers, lack of interest of students, only oral communication, and lack of practical activities are the difficulties in communicating science. Eupena (2012) found a similar result that the classroom environment may be unworkable since teachers sometimes underestimate the importance of noisy students for their work if they don't respond correctly. Dhindsa (2005) also suggested a similar impact on the trust of the students in learning. Gestures such as head shaking, facial gestures, and communication with the eyes showed the students' excitement, approval, and comprehension to aid those ideas and add value to the students' attitude or result towards studying science. Similar results were also the findings of a study conducted by Ruesch and Kees (1974) on teacher interaction and communication about science application and enhance students concepts; make them comfortable. Xie et al. (2008) investigated communications and found the results that maintaining a smile on face found closely to express the students' actions, and the present study also found similar results. Teachers in the classroom used movements to explain the contents of the lecture, illustrating particular points and thereby maintaining interest provided that visual meaning of science applications. Also As the communication through various methods progressed; the teachers might modify and perform various instructional sequences of skills according to the class's needs. Moreover, the teaching in learning abilities through the communicating science strengthened the professional growth of the student's school and society

similar to findings and provides new inputs as well (Eupena, 2012). Thus Science communication skills and behavior, including challenge, encouragement and respect, of science teachers and learning dishonest cooperation and climate management affected learning of science. In contrast, students who suggested that teachers modify their actions based on students' observations and diverse experiences, aspirations, skills, and abilities differed from the approach to science.

Conclusions

The interview data findings indicate that educational achievements and social development can be built up through science communication. Science creates students' awareness of which direction they can move in the future and can influence student's and society's behavior and policy priorities. Science affects people's lives, such as vaccination, medical care, education, food, etc. The communicating and learning process uses a combination of graph, text, sound, and video. Computer-assisted instructions apply to nearly any application, such as exercises, simulations, teaching exercises, additional exercises, instructional management, database creation and programming. They also agreed that science communication enhances students' concepts in building up their understating, thus impacting the broader community of schools and society. The various difficulties in science communication were noted. At the school level, lack of facilities and technology, lack of experience of teachers, lack of interest of students, only oral communication, and lack of practical activities are the difficulties in communicating science. Most of the students belonged to rural areas; therefore, they were facing language issues. Most students feel difficult to understand English terminologies and less resource material, not project-based learning. We can overcome these difficulties by giving proper facilities and proper training to teachers, performing activities, increasing professional qualifications of teachers, developing the interest of science education in students, and making an appropriate environment for science communication.

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